
ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ НАУКИ

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FEATURES OF CREATIVE ACTIONS OF PRIMARY SCHOOL GRADUATES

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The object of study in this work is the creative thinking of elementary school students, in particular, fourth-graders. The subject of the study is the features of children's creative actions in the external and internal plans when compiling tasks on non-educational material. In a study in the conditions of individual experiments with 110 fourth-grade students, the author's method, conditionally called "Postman", was used. This technique includes tasks in which it is required to search for the routes of movement of an imaginary character "postman" on the playing field of a labyrinth type based on the proposed rules. As a result, four types of creative actions were singled out when composing tasks (formal, meaningful, productive, original) and it was established that the condition for the use of one or another type of creative actions by children is the form of action when composing tasks, either externally or internally. In the first case, children more often use creative actions of a meaningful, productive and original type than when compiling tasks in the internal plan.

Key words: *elementary school graduates, searching for movements in the maze, creative actions when compiling tasks.*

Introduction.

The study of the features of the formation of creative actions during the period of primary education as an important form of independent cognitive activity of schoolchildren is an important aspect in the development of topical problems of pedagogical psychology. At the same time, the formation of independent actions of children (including creative ones) is one of the important pedagogical tasks set for school education in the new Federal State Educational Standard of Primary General Education [6].

The named Standard formulates the urgent need for the formation of independent actions among schoolchildren related to setting new cognitive tasks, planning methods for achieving the required results, choosing effective approaches to solving educational problems, and meaningfully correlating the actions performed and the intended results, with the adjustment of their own actions in solving problems, with the justification of the methods used in achieving the selected goals.

The initial idea of the performed experimental research is connected with the study of independent creative actions in fourth-graders associated with their proposal of new tasks built on non-educational material.

The purpose of the work was to establish the characteristics of the creative actions that fourth-graders perform when they offer new tasks. At the same time, in the course of individual experiments, different forms of action were used when creating new tasks - subject-effective and visual-figurative.

The study was based on the assumption that creative actions performed in an objective-active form are more effective than creative actions performed in a visual-figurative form. In this, we proceeded from fundamental provisions about the nature of mental (in particular, cognitive) development in ontogeny. In accordance with these provisions, effective actions with images of objects are formed later than effective actions with the objects themselves (see, for example, [4, 5]).

2. Materials and methods.

An experimental study was carried out on the basis of labyrinth problems "with rules". In these problems (in contrast to labyrinth problems "without rules", where the search for a route from "entrance" to "exit" is based only on the perception of dead ends and free passages), the search for a solution is determined only by the rule of moving through the elements of the labyrinth (for the application of problems of this type, see below). in our works [1, 2, 3].

In the study, we used such labyrinth problems "with rules", in which it was required to find out which lines of the labyrinth can be used to get from one point to another in the required number of actions (steps). Moving along the lines of the labyrinth was carried out according to the rules based on the coincidence of individual geometric figures of the compared images (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Playing field 1.

For example, if lines (Fig. 1) connect circles where there is an identical figure, then it is possible to move along such lines (acting mentally), and if there is no identical figure in circles, then it is impossible to move. So, in this example, you can move between circles 1 and 2, 1 and 4, 3 and 6, 5 and 6, but you cannot move between circles 2 and 3, 2 and 5, 4 and 5.

Two series of experiments were carried out with problems of this kind. In each of them, it was first necessary to solve such problems, and then propose new ones.

In the first series, the children were asked to act on the external plane, as in solving as well as problem solving.

First, the training problem was solved. To do this, the child was asked to familiarize himself with a labyrinth of 16 circles, each of which had two images, while for some circles the images coincided, repeated (see, for example, circles 1 and 2), and for some circles both images were different (see, for example, circles 2 and 7 in Fig. 2).

At the beginning of the experiment, the child's attention was drawn to the fact that there are two different images in each circle, and they were asked to name them: a circle, a square, an oblique square (parallelogram), a quadrangle (trapezoid), etc. Then they indicated that there are lines between the circles that each circle is indicated by a number placed in the lower left corner, and that there are 16 circles in the figure.

The rule for moving between circles along lines was reported as a game rule "postman", in which it was assumed that the circles are houses where two inhabitants live (there are two images each) and that along the lines between the circles (as in "paths"), the "postman" walks according to the following rule: if the path connects houses where there is an identical resident, then you can go along such a path (for example, circles 1 and 2), and if the path connects houses where there is no

identical resident, then such a path cannot be walked, (for example, along the path between circles 3 and 6).

Fig. 2. Playing field 2.

The playing field offered to the subject for solving and creating new problems was drawn on a separate sheet of paper, where each circle was 3 cm by 3 cm, and the vertical and horizontal lines between the circles were 4 cm. In the first two series, where the solution and inventing tasks were performed externally, the subject was asked to use a cube to find the lines along which the postman moved between the initial and final houses (circles), and two circles made of transparent material (in particular, made of solid polyethylene) to mark the initial and final points of movement "postman".

After familiarizing the subject with the characteristics of the playing field, the features of the combinations of two images in each drawing and the rules for moving the "postman", he was asked to complete a training task: to pass in accordance with the rule for moving the "postman" from circle 4 to circle 13. To do this, he was asked to cover with plastic mugs circle 4 and circle 13, thus denoting the start and end points of the movements, and the movements themselves along the lines - "paths" to make by moving the cube, touching the surface of the sheet on which the playing field was drawn. If the child was wrong, he was reminded of the rule "postman".

After completing the training task at the second stage of the experiment, the child was asked to solve two main tasks: task No. 1 (first degree of complexity): "What two paths did the "postman" go from circle 1 to circle 11?" (Fig. 3) and task No. 2 (second degree of complexity): "What three paths did the "postman" go from circle 5 to circle 12?" (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. Task №1.

Fig. 4. Task №2.

At the third stage of the experiment, if the subject coped with tasks No. 1 and No. 2, he was asked to come up with tasks of the first degree of complexity (i.e., those where, as in task No. 1, it was necessary to find two paths). At the same time, to the left of him, on the table, there was a sheet with a playing field, where circles 1 and 11 were covered with polyethylene circles, i.e. the condition of problem No. 1 played the role of a model.

To perform creative actions to create new tasks, he was also given sheets of paper with a playing field, plastic mugs and a cube.

The child was told: “Now you will come up with tasks yourself, where you need to find two paths along which the postman walked. You have already solved this problem. Come up with as many tasks as you want. Saying this, the experimenter pointed to the playing field located on the table with the conditions of the main task No. 1, where circles 1 and 11 were covered with plastic circles. Thus, the subjects were asked to come up with tasks of the first degree of complexity, similar to task No. 1.

One of the sheets of paper with the playing field was located directly in front of the child and he was told: “Think about which circles the postman walked two paths between and cover these circles with circles. This will turn out to be a problem where you need to find two paths”.

Thus, the children of both subgroups of the third group composed several tasks, but constructed in the same way, according to one or another template. Performing creative actions, the children acted in different ways. The first group implemented a formal approach in their actions, since the children proposed tasks that could not be solved by finding only two paths. In this case, the children simply covered the numbers of the starting and ending points of the route with circles. "postman", without checking how many tracks the "postman" needs to go to get from the starting point to the final one.

As a rule, these children made up tasks not of the first, but of the second degree of complexity (that is, those where it is required to find three paths, and not two, as suggested to the subjects) (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. Task of the second degree of complexity.

For the subjects of this group, the following actions were characteristic. Looking at the condition of problem No. 1 on the playing field located on the table on the left, they, as one could notice, noted (sometimes even aloud) that both “covered” circles were on the same straight line. After that, circles 2 and 12 or 5 and 15 were covered with circles on their playing field, located next to circles 1 and 11 from problem No. 1. After that, they said that the task was invented. Thus, we can assume that they focused only on the external features of the sample problem, without clarifying the features of its construction.

The subjects of the second group acted meaningfully - they made up one or two correct tasks that can be solved, for example, such a task (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6. Task №1.

Unlike the children of the previous group, they did not just look at the conditions of problem No. 1, but, as you could see, they studied it, remembering their solution: sometimes they simply said: "... the circle is repeated first, then the pentagon ...", sometimes they were drawn along the lines between circles 1 - 6 and 6 - 11 with a finger or a cube.

Then they turned to the proposed playing field, covered some circle on it with a circle, for example, circle 2 and moved the cube first to circle 3, and then to circle 4. Then they covered circle 4 with a circle.

When the experimenter asked for the conditions of the problem, they usually said: "We need to find out how the postman got from house 2 to house 4".

After that, the experimenter set aside the playing field with the conditions of the first problem and asked the child if he wanted to compose more problems. If the child agreed, then he was asked to take another playing field. When compiling the second task, the children acted in the same way as when compiling the first. As a result, circles marked the beginning and end of the "postman's" movements.

The children of the third group also offered solvable problems, but not one or two (like the children of the second group), but three or five. They thus acted productively. At the same time, starting to compose tasks, they, like the children of the second group, first considered the condition of the sample task (task No. 1), highlighting two paths there, and then offered the first task.

Some of the children in this group (subgroup A), composing the first problem, drew a cube along the lines from circle 5 to circle 6 and from it to circle 7, and covered circles 5 and 7 with circles (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. The first task of subgroup A.

Then, taking the second playing field, they looked at the condition of the first proposed problem and, after inventing the second problem, they drew a cube along the lines between circles 9–10 and 10–11, covering circles 9 and 11 with circles (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8. The second task of subgroup A.

Then they took the third playing field and acted in the same way as in the preparation of the second problem: they combined circles 13–14–15, covering circles 13 and 15 with circles (Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. The third task of subgroup A.

Other children in this group (subgroup B) drew a cube along the lines from circle 1 to circle 5 and from it to circle 9, covering circles 1 and 9 with circles (Fig. 10).

Fig. 10. The first task of subgroup B.

Then they looked at the condition of the first proposed problem and after that they drew a cube along the lines between circles 2 - 6 and 6 - 10, covering circles 2 and 10 with circles (Fig. 11).

Fig. 11. The second task of subgroup B.

Then they also acted in the course of creating the third task: they combined circles 3 - 7 - 11, covering circles 3 and 11 with circles (Fig. 12).

Fig. 12. The third task of subgroup A.

The children of the fourth group, like the children of the third group, proposed several (three to five) tasks, but these tasks were constructed differently: the location of the initial and final circles in these tasks had different spatial orientations. The children of this group thus created a variety of tasks and carried out, in our opinion, not only productive, but also original creative actions.

Such behavior was typical for the children of this group. When creating the first task, they acted in the same way as the children of the third group: first, they considered the condition of the sample task (task No. 1), highlighting two paths there, and then offered the first task, where "postman" moved vertically (Fig. 13).

Fig. 13. The first task of the fourth group.

Further, taking the second playing field, they, in contrast to the children of the third group, looked not only at the condition of the first task they proposed, but, as could be observed, compared this condition with the condition of the problem No. 1 they solved (i.e., the sample problem). As a result, the second task turned out for them, not the same as the first one - in it the "postman" moved along a broken line, horizontally and diagonally (Fig. 14).

Fig. 14. The second task of the fourth group.

In the course of inventing the third task, they, having taken the third playing field, compared the conditions of the three tasks, - task No. 1 and the two tasks proposed earlier. As a result, the third task differed from the first two and the sample task, in which the “postman” moved horizontally (Fig. 15).

Fig. 15. The third task of the fourth group.

In the second series of experiments, in contrast to the first series, it was proposed to solve and invent problems in the internal plan. This meant that the child was not allowed to touch the lines of the playing field and circles with images, and the solution of the problems they were given, and the conditions of new problems, could only be written down on a piece of paper.

After examining the playing field by the child, mastering the rule of the "postman" and completing the training task orally, it was proposed to solve problems in writing, only looking at the playing field, below which the condition of the problem was located.

To solve problem No. 1, its condition was proposed on a sheet of paper in the following form (Fig. 16).

Fig. 16. Condition of task No.1.

The child was told: “Guess which two paths the postman took from house 1 to house 11?” and indicated: “Write in an empty rectangle the number of the circle into which the postman came from circle 1 and from which he then got into circle 11.”

As a result of reflection, he could enter the correct answer in the empty rectangle, - intermediate circle 6 (Fig. 17).

Fig. 17. Solution of problem No.1.

To solve problem No. 2 on another sheet of paper, its condition was also proposed in writing (Fig. 18).

Fig. 18. Condition of task №2.

The child was told: “Guess what three paths the postman took from house 5 to house 12?” and pointed out: “Write in the empty rectangles the numbers of the two circles in which the postman had to come in to get from circle 5 to circle 12.”

With a successful solution, the child entered the numbers of both intermediate circles, 6 and 11, into the empty rectangles (Fig. 19).

Fig. 19. Solution of problem No. 2.

If the subject coped with tasks No. 1 and No. 2, he was asked to compose tasks of the first degree of complexity (i.e., those where, as in task No. 1, it was necessary to find two tracks).

At the same time, to the left of him on the table there was a sheet with the condition of problem No. 1.

To come up with problems, the child was given a sheet of paper on which a playing field and a form (a row of several empty rectangles) were placed to create conditions for problems of varying complexity.

The child was told: "Now you will come up with tasks yourself, where you need to find two paths along which the postman walked. You have already solved this problem. Come up with as many tasks as you want. Saying this, the experimenter pointed to a sheet located on the table on the left with the playing field and the conditions of the main task No. 1 (Fig. 3). Thus, the subjects were asked to come up with tasks of the first degree of complexity, similar to task No. 1.

One of the sheets of paper with a playing field and a form for creating a task condition was located directly in front of the child and he was told: "Think about which circles the postman walked two paths between and write the numbers of these circles in the empty rectangles on the left and right, and leave the middle rectangle empty for writing solutions. This will turn out to be a problem where you need to find two paths. Saying this, the experimenter points to the sheet with the condition of problem No. 1, located on the left.

In the course of inventing tasks, the children acted in different ways. The first group (as in the previous series) implemented a formal approach in their actions, proposing problems that could not be solved by discovering only two paths. At the same time, they did not study the condition of problem No. 1 (on the sheet located on the left) and simply wrote down (as it was shown in the condition of problem No. 1) in the extreme rectangles (in the lower part on their sheet) the numbers of circles between which, in their opinion, the postman could walk two lanes - they did not check how many lanes actually need to be walked "postman" to get from the starting point to the final one. Most often, they proposed tasks with three tracks (see, for example, Fig. 6).

The subjects of the second group acted meaningfully - they (just like the children of this group in the first series) first studied the condition of problem No. 1, remembering their solution, and then made up one or two correct problems that could be solved (see, for example, Fig. 6).

The children of the third group also composed tasks to be solved, but not one or two (like the children of the second group), but three to five. They (like the children of this group in the first series) acted productively: first, they studied the condition of the sample problem (problem No. 1), highlighting two paths there, and then they offered the first problem.

Just as in the first series, some children in this group (subgroup A) offered identically structured tasks in which the "postman" moved along the horizontal lines of the playing field (see, for example, Fig. 7, 8, 9), other children (subgroup B) also offered tasks based on the same template, but in these tasks the "postman" moved along vertical lines (see, for example, Fig. 10, 11, 12).

The children of the fourth group (just like in the first series) carried out original creative actions, since they offered several (three to five) tasks, but these tasks were constructed differently:

the location of the initial and final circles in these problems had different spatial orientations (see, for example, Fig. 13, 14, 15).

3. Results.

Among pupils of the fourth grade, 56 people participated in the first series, 54 - in the second. The data obtained in individual experiments of both research series are presented in the table 1.

Table 1. Types of creative actions performed by fourth-graders in the first and second series.

Series	Types of creative actions			
	Formal	Informative	Productive	Original
First	12 (22.2%)	28 (51.8%)*	4 (7.5%)*	4 (7.2%)
Second	10 (18.5%)	2 (3.6%)	38 (67.8%)*	12 (21.4%)*

Note: * $p < 0.05$.

Analysis of the data presented in the table allows us to note the following.

First, the results obtained indicate the number of children who performed productive creative actions in each series.

In the first series, the number of children who performed the noted actions is 67.8%, in the second series the number of such children is 51.8%, the difference in the noted indicators is statistically significant (at $p < 0.05$).

Secondly, the results of the experiments indicate the number of children who performed original creative actions in each series.

In the first series, the number of children who performed the noted actions is 21.4%; in the second series, the number of such children is 7.5%; the difference in the noted indicators is statistically significant (at $p < 0.05$).

Thirdly, the results of the study indicate the number of children who carried out productive and original creative actions in each series.

In the first series, the number of children who performed the noted actions is 89.2%, and in the second series, the number of such children is 59.3% - the difference in the noted indicators is statistically significant (at $p < 0.01$).

Thus, the data obtained in the course of individual experiments with fourth-graders confirm the initial hypothesis of the study that creative actions performed in an objective-active form are more effective than creative actions performed in a visual-figurative form.

4. Discussion.

1. Experiment conditions

As noted, 110 fourth-graders took part in individual experiments of both series of the study. Children solved and independently composed tasks on non-educational material - labyrinth tasks "with rules".

At the same time, the conditions were created for the students to solve and compose problems of varying complexity in two forms of action: externally and internally.

In the first case, the child could touch the playing field and, with the help of the proposed items (cardboard mugs and a cube), outline possible routes for the movement of the imaginary character "postman".

In the second case, it was impossible to touch the playing field and use the offered items, but it was required to act by mentally imagining the possible routes of movement of the "postman".

2. The scientific significance of the study

In this study, for the first time, four approaches were identified in the implementation of creative actions among younger schoolchildren (in particular, among fourth-graders).

In one case, the children acted formally, composing problems that could not be solved on the basis of the proposed conditions.

In another case, the children acted meaningfully, composing one or two tasks that had a solution on the basis of the proposed conditions.

In the third case, the children acted not only in a meaningful way, composing tasks to be solved, but also productively, since they proposed three to five tasks, but they were constructed in the same way, according to a single scheme.

In the fourth case, the children acted not only productively, but also in an original way, since they offered three to five tasks constructed in different ways.

It is also important to note that the study also showed for the first time the distribution of the noted four approaches in the implementation of creative actions among fourth-graders.

3. Research limitations

The above conditions for conducting individual experiments oblige children to act not in any way, but in a very definite way.

It can be assumed that under other conditions for conducting experiments, for example, if there are other rules for moving around the maze or if there are not 16 compared objects on the playing field, but 12 or 20 objects, and also when not one hundred people, but several hundreds or thousands - the results of the distribution of four approaches among fourth-graders in composing problems would be different.

4. Research prospects

In the future, it is necessary to determine the nature of the relationship between the distribution of four types of creative actions and the age characteristics of children.

In this regard, it is planned to conduct individual experiments on the material of labyrinth tasks “with rules” (“postman”) with younger students studying in the first, second and third grades, as well as with younger teenagers (fifth and sixth grades) and older teenagers (seventh - ninth grades).

At the same time, in order to clarify the nature of the distribution of the identified types of creative actions, it is necessary to conduct individual experiments with fourth-graders with tasks of a different type, in particular, with spatial-combinatorial and plot-logical tasks.

5. Conclusion.

As noted, the study under consideration was aimed at clarifying the question of what types of creative actions fourth-graders use when compiling new tasks, in particular, on non-educational material.

As a result of individual experiments with 110 fourth-grade schoolchildren, it was found that when composing problems, children use four types of creative actions: formal, meaningful, productive and original.

At the same time, it is important to note that the use of the noted types of creative actions depends on the form of the action (subject-effective or visual-figurative), in which children are invited to come up with tasks. In particular, it has been shown that productive and original actions are performed more successfully in a subject-effective form than in a visual-figurative one.

On the whole, based on the fact that the majority of fourth-graders use productive creative actions, there is reason to assert that, in relation to labyrinth tasks “with rules”, primary school education contributes to the formation of this particular type of creative actions to a greater extent. It can be assumed that the use of original creative actions will be typical for most schoolchildren later, in the fifth or sixth grades of high school.

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